

Research

Examining the Role of Organizational Politics on Disruptive Employee Behavior in Banks

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Abstract: This study delves into the intricacies of employee behavior within organizations, seeking to uncover the root causes of negative conduct and how to effectively address it. By doing so, the research aims to enhance individual and collective productivity. The insights drawn from this study hold the potential to offer practical and theoretical advancements that will guide organizations in fostering a more productive and harmonious work environment.

The research methodology employed here involves a comprehensive analysis of perceived organizational politics and its correlation with Disruptive Employee Behavior. This analysis is extended to encompass antecedent factors such as passive leadership, organizational trust, and relationship conflict. To gather the necessary data, a survey questionnaire was utilized as the primary data collection tool. A total of 350 questionnaires were distributed among various organizations, out of which 294 were effectively collected for analysis, reflecting a response rate of 84.46 percent.

The findings of this study affirm a robust connection between perceived organizational politics and disruptive Employee Behavior. Through statistical analyses, it became evident that factors like passive leadership, organizational trust, and relationship conflict are significant contributors to this dynamic. The study underscores the importance of recognizing these associations to create a conducive work environment that minimizes disruptive behavior and maximizes productivity. Organizations can benefit from a heightened awareness of perceived organizational politics and its impact on behavior, allowing them to foster a more positive and productive atmosphere. By addressing issues related to passive leadership, trust, and relationship conflict, organizations can proactively mitigate negative employee behavior, thus promoting a culture of harmony and efficiency.

This research not only sheds light on the complexities of employee behavior within organizations but also serves as a roadmap for cultivating a healthier workplace. The study's insights provide valuable guidance for organizations to address disruptive behavior by understanding its underlying causes. Ultimately, this research contributes to the collective effort of creating workplaces that empower employees, foster trust, and boost overall organizational success. The groundwork laid here also sets the stage for future research inquiries in this critical domain.

Keywords: Organizational politics, workplace, passive leadership, relationship conflict

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Introduction

In today's highly competitive world, organizations strive to gain a vying advantage over their rivals. This pursuit of excellence extends to employees within these organizations, as they are expected to outperform their colleagues [1]. [2] assert that the influence of politics in organizations has become significant enough to be considered a means of control. The intense desire to outperform others often drives individuals to employ both legal and illegal tactics. They form alliances and employ deceptive techniques to undermine their peers, relentlessly pursuing personal advancement at the expense of others' emotions and possessions. This phenomenon is commonly known as Organizational politics. Some scholars view politics as a pragmatic approach utilized by both employees and managers to accomplish their objectives [3]. While it is challenging to quantify the extent of political behavior within an organization, there is a prevailing perception that uncivil behavior is occurring, leading to harm for the organization as a whole. Therefore, gaining a understanding of Organizational dynamics necessitates an understanding of politics within the organization [4]. Despite assertions from various studies that Organizational politics is pervasive, it requires further attention and empirical investigation [5]. The perception of Organizational politics is a prevalent experience that every employee encounters on a daily basis in the workplace. It serves as a source of psychological distress and creates an unpleasant atmosphere for individuals to perform their work. This phenomenon arises from various factors, including conflicting interests, limited resources, intensifying competition, and power struggles [6]. When the perception of politics permeates an organization, it often leads to Disruptive Employee Behavior, where individuals no longer engage in civil and courteous behavior towards one another. People naturally desire to be treated with respect, and those who receive respect are more likely to be inspired and loyal to their work and the organization. However, due to the Perceived Organizational Politics, individuals often feel alienated and disrespected. [7] define Organizational politics as a process in which individuals organize and simplify their sensory impressions to attribute meaning to their surroundings. Other related definitions describe Organizational politics as the exertion of power through various means [8]. Various studies have focused on deviant behaviors such as workplace aggression, harassment, bullying, and oppression. However, there has been comparatively less research attention given to milder forms of mistreatment, specifically Disruptive Employee Behavior, which has a significant potential to affect employees of the organization at all levels. This contagious behavior can ultimately influence the entire organization from bottom-line employees to top-line managers. According [9], even surveys indicate that incivility is a prevalent issue, with neglected incidence rates reaching as high as 90%. Several factors contribute to the insight of a political climate within an organization, including passive leadership, relationship conflicts, and lack of Organizational trust.

Organizational performance and the functioning of managers and employees are greatly influenced by leadership. Poor leadership can have a destructive effect on the organization, while the absence of leadership, known as passive leadership or laissez-faire leadership, can also lead to Organizational failure. Both leadership and the perception of Organizational politics are compelling antecedents that can impact employees' attitudes and behaviors towards their job. As [10] states, the entire organization is influenced by the attitudes of its leaders, and employees look to them as examples of what constitutes acceptable conduct. Passive leadership, characterized by the failure to take action or exhibit leadership qualities, is an environmental factor that contributes to the perception of Organizational politics.

Passive leadership gives rise to vulnerability to work-related stressors and is resentfully associated with crucial personal and Organizational outcomes, fostering impolite, disrespectful, and discourteous behaviors within the organization. Incivility, including disrespectful behavior, has become prevalent across various domains of modern society, including the business world, which was once considered a bastion of professionalism [11]. [12], [13], and [14] suggest that effective leadership involves navigating a number of tasks, multidimensional roles, and complexity, which can be explained as the art of leading. The widespread occurrence of disruptive employee behavior is concerning because it imposes significant costs on targeted employees, their coworkers, and organizations as a whole. In this study, we

hypothesize that passive management directly influences employees' perception of a political climate within the organization, thereby creating significant disturbances within the organization.

Teamwork has become increasingly important in organizations; however, effective collaboration in teams often faces challenges. The main challenge in working in teams is the presence of conflicts among team members, which can arise due to various reasons.

Relationship conflict, in particular, disrupts the normal functioning of the organization when employees share individual concerns with one another, leading to clashes of interest. Dirks and [15] describe relationship conflict as diminishing the information processing ability of a group because, rather than working on tasks-related issues, members devote their time and energy to focus on one another and devising strategies to undermine one another.

Organizational trust is an emotional state that fosters employee motivation and commitment towards their work. However, if that trust is broken, employees may develop negative intentions towards the organization, perceiving it as being against them and engaging in conspiracies. This marks the beginning of the perception of a political climate within the organization, which then leads to disruptive employee behavior by [16], [17]. Incivility involves employees deliberately harming the organization and other individuals' emotions and behaving inappropriately towards them. The lack of Organizational trust, resulting from a deficiency in predictability and a sense of feeling unsafe, leads to reduced Organizational dedication. Trust is a fragile element that takes time to build but can be shattered in an instant. Moreover, trust plays a crucial role as a predictor of satisfaction with governance and performance appraisal.

Employee behaviors and Organizational productivity are directly influenced by Organizational trust. Mild forms of incivility are typically associated with the beginning stages of trust in management. Establishing trust is a crucial aspect of successful work-related relationships [18]. Scholars have observed that trust in the organization and management is linked to reduced counterproductive work behaviors such as absent-mindedness, aggression, lateness, and contributes to overall better performance. Given the delicate nature of trust within organizations, management should promote it among employees and take steps to prevent negative communication that could erode trust within the workplace [19].

Literature Review

1. Evolution of Perceived Organizational Politics: A Historical Perspective

The perception of Organizational politics is a complex and informal experience that can significantly impact the smooth functioning of an organization. It often leads to a disturbance among employees, fostering feelings of envy and negative intentions towards the organization. While politics is a prevalent aspect in all organizations, its implications can be both positive and negative. Therefore, it becomes essential to comprehend the dynamics of Organizational politics to gain a comprehensive understanding of its effects [20]. Numerous scholars have dedicated significant efforts to studying the concept on perception of Organizational politics, with many agreeing that the political dynamics within an organization are highly significant [21]. Extensive research shows Perceived Organizational Politics (POP) requires attention as it involves the observer's assessments of an individual's motivations for their actions.

Therefore, studying Organizational politics is a valuable and challenging area of research. Exploring this topic enables organizations to develop novel strategies for effectively traversing political dynamics. It is important to acknowledge that individuals are inherently political beings. The Greek word "Politika," which means 'affairs of the cities' is the source of the word "politics". It encompasses the process of going with choices that apply to individuals from a group. From the moment individuals interact with others, they engage in political dynamics because politics involves determining the rules that govern inter-personal relationships when people live and interact with each other to fulfill their needs. People's subjective perceptions, emotions, and interpretations form the basis of research on political phenomena [22]. Organizational politics is integral to the functioning of an organization, particularly in a changing environment. The evolving Organizational landscape has made organizations more susceptible to acts of politics [1]. Organizational politics plays a pivotal role in addressing and clarifying issues within an organization that may lack

clear definitions [23]. When employees look at organizational politics, it frequently has a negative connotation and manifests in a negative way. Organizational politics has a historical basis, with Aristotle describing it as a result of differing interests among individuals that require prompt resolution. When logical reasoning fails, many executives resort to political tactics to gain compliance. Despite the negative perception of Organizational politics, there is evidence that suggests it is not always inherently bad, and political skill, when used effectively, can help achieve compromises in challenging workplace situations [24]. However, even though political dynamics may not always be harmful, they can waste time in organizations and distract staff from focusing on their job performance. Managers often spend time trying to deal with political issues, and ineffective politics can harm the image of an organization, leading managers to lose interest in utilizing political skills within the workplace. This creates a negative spiral of reciprocal behavior, as the perception and understanding of benefits and offers vary among employees and power players in organizations [25]. Moreover, when employees engage in imbalanced political behavior, they may become less committed to their organization, leading to a decline in overall task performance. It becomes particularly detrimental when employees engage in self-serving behavior that goes against Organizational norms, such as lobbying for special favors from senior management. These types of political behaviors undermine the ethical climate within the organization and can be unfair to those who stick to proper procedures, potentially influencing attitudes and behaviors in the workplace.

Perception of Organizational politics also has negative impacts, such as disruptive employee behavior. In developing nations, the situation often worsens due to limited opportunities, competition, and ineffective Organizational policies. The theoretical framework surrounding the perception of a political organization is evident in the efforts made by individuals or organizations to promote or defend personal interests through influence or other tactics, especially in uncertain and ambiguous Organizational settings. Practices related to work are not necessarily seen as consistently negative or outside the boundaries of informal or formal business norms. According to [26], a negative outcome of perceived Organizational politics is the belief that the organization does not acknowledge high work standards, challenging tasks, and integrity.

Another theoretical approach, known as the Organizational behavior approach, differs from the negative perspective. This approach, largely based on negative empirical studies, seeks to demonstrate a view of Organizational politics as inherently harmful and contrary to the goals and objectives of the organization. However, research has shown that at least some level of Organizational politics is inevitable and intrinsic. The literature presents three perspectives on Organizational politics: nature, determinants, and consequences [27].

2. Categories of Perceived Organizational Politics

Several theorists have made attempts to classify the dimensions of Organizational politics due to its significance in Organizational settings. Here are some of the key classifications:

1). Three- Dimensional Classification

[28] proposed a classification of political ways of behaving in view of three aspects:

- 1. Legitimate-Illegitimate Dimension:** This dimension categorizes political behaviors based on whether they are considered minor day-to-day acts or more significant and destructive actions within the organization.
- 2. Internal-External Dimension:** This dimension distinguishes between political behaviors that involve using Organizational resources internally (within the organization) and those that involve using Organizational resources externally (outside the organization).
- 3. Vertical-Lateral Dimension:** This dimension classifies political behaviors based on the level of hierarchy to which they belong. Vertical resources refer to behaviors that involve seeking favors or influencing those in higher positions (e.g., asking for a favor from a supervisor). Lateral resources refer to behaviors that involve derogatory remarks or alliances with colleagues at the same level of hierarchy.

Based on the dimensions, Farrell and Petersen proposed eight clusters of Organizational political acts: legitimate lateral-external, legitimate vertical-external, illegitimate vertical-internal, legitimate lateral-internal, illegitimate lateral-internal, illegitimate

lateral-external, illegitimate vertical-external, and legitimate vertical-internal. These clusters help in understanding the different types and manifestations of political behaviors within organizations.

2). Five-Dimensional Classification

[29] developed a classification scheme for Perceived Organizational Politics (POP) based on a factor analysis. The analysis revealed five dimensions: key others, clarity, distortion, rewards, and image.

1. **Key Others:** Perceived Organizational Politics (POP) dimension focused on the influence and power of key individuals within the organization.
2. **Clarity:** This dimension reflects the perceived transparency and clear communication of organizational decisions and actions.
3. **Distortion:** Distortion pertains to the manipulation or misrepresentation of information within the organizational context.
4. **Rewards:** The rewards dimension involves the perception of unfair distribution of rewards and recognition.
5. **Image:** Image dimension relates to how individuals perceive their own image and reputation in the organizational setting.

This classification scheme helps in understanding the different facets and manifestations of Perceived Organizational Politics, providing insights into how individuals perceive and experience political behaviors in their work environment [29].

3). Three-Factor Classification

The three-factor classification system proposed by [30] is widely recognized among scholars and researchers studying Perceived Organizational Politics (POP). They conducted a study using a 31-item scale of POP and employed factor analysis to identify five factors: POP in relation to coworkers and supervisors, general political behavior, pay and promotions, and going along to get ahead. The scale was further refined until it had a 12-item, three-factor structure that was widely used in research.

The three categories of POP identified by Kacmar and Ferris are as follows:

1. **Pay and Promotion Politics:** This category pertains to political behaviors related to the pay and promotion processes within the organization. It examines whether rewards and benefits are based on merit or influenced by political activities such as favoritism. Employees perceive high levels of "pay and promotion politics" when they believe that rewards and benefits are unjustly allocated based on political factors.
2. **Go Along to Get Ahead:** This category encompasses behaviors where individuals remain passive and do not take actions that may disrupt the status quo. Non-threatening individuals who avoid confrontation are often rewarded, as they do not challenge or interfere with the actions of influential others. This behavior ensures the preservation of the perceiver's perceived status and safety.
3. **General Political Behavior:** This category includes a range of political behaviors aimed at achieving desired outcomes. These behaviors arise in situations where there is uncertainty or lack of clear rules, and individuals seek to obtain scarce resources. Examples include criticize others for mistakes, taking credit for colleagues' work, and aligning oneself with influential individuals in the organization. Such behaviors are considered self-serving as they aim to achieve desired outcomes

Given the significance of perceived Organizational politics in Organizational settings, researchers have focused on understanding the factors contributing to its perception. Political systems have been seen in different parts of authoritative life, such as technique plan and execution, leader the board and across all levels of the association.

In the research model under discussion, perceived Organizational politics is influenced by passive leadership, Organizational trust, and relationship conflict, ultimately leading to disruptive employee behavior. This model aims to justify the selection of variables and establish research hypotheses.

3. Antecedents of Perceived Organizational Politics

1.5.3.1. *Passive Leadership*

While most leadership studies focus on positive leadership styles, the negative aspects of leadership have often been overlooked [31]. Passive leaders are identified in the literature as displaying behaviors such as delaying important decisions, ignoring workplace issues, and failing to communicate expected standards of behavior to employees. This type of leadership falls under a *laissez-faire* approach, where leaders adopt a hands-off and non-interventionist management style [32]. [33] describe passive leadership as a "wait and see" approach, where action is only taken when mistakes occur or problems reach an unavoidable level. Some researchers characterize this approach as involving passivity, inertia, avoidance, and shirking responsibilities. Passive leaders often don't make decisions, don't recognize and motivate employees, and don't take into account what each employee needs. For example, passive leadership includes cases where a leader neglects a subordinate's well-being, such as in a workplace with safety hazards, or intentionally arrives late to a meeting organized by one of the subordinates [34]. According to some researchers, passive leadership can also contribute to administrative bullying and disruptive employee behavior. Lack of involvement and engagement from employees can lead to persistent and escalating problems among them, sometimes resulting in someone being bullied within the organization. [35] suggests that employees' uncivil and aggressive behavior may be encouraged by *laissez-faire* management, resulting in the mistreatment of specific individuals within workgroups. When a manager neglects their responsibility to address social conflicts among employees, these conflicts can intensify and create a culture that tolerates hostile conduct in the workforce. Passive leaders often have limited personal involvement and connection with employees, leading to a sense of social exclusion and being ignored [36]. Studies indicate that passive leaders are resistant to change and innovation within the organization, preferring to maintain the status quo and perceiving novelty and creativity as threats to customary values [37]. Various studies have shown that this style of leadership is negatively related to related outcomes [38].

1.5.3.2. *Organizational Trust*

Scholars have made efforts to more readily figure out trust and have distinguished it as both quality and an interaction [39]. Trait-based trust refers to the singular attributes developed during childhood, where seeking and receiving help from loved ones leads to a general tendency to trust others [40]. The Personality-based trust model suggests that individuals have varying levels of trust and tend to develop trust when interacting with others, leading to positive beliefs about their intentions [41]. On the other hand, trust is defined as an emerging state as a combination of motivational, cognitive, or affective states that can change in response to inputs, processes, and outcomes [42]. Trust is viewed as an attitude that can develop rapidly over time as a result of specific interactions in various situations [43]. Trust is also seen as an intervening mechanism that weakens other attitudes [44].

1.5.3.3. *Relationship Conflict*

When individuals come together in groups, they often face issues related to both task-related matters and interpersonal relationships [45]. The latter, known as relationship conflict, arises due to personal preferences, values, and beliefs, which can hinder the productivity of teams as conflicts of interest emerge among group members.

Previous research [46] has found that relationship conflict inevitably affects overall job performance. Relationship conflict, also known as emotional or affective conflict, refers to socioemotional or relational differences, clashes, or poor social interactions that involve negative emotions such as anxiety, frustration, and animosity among individuals on an individual level. Relationship conflict within the workplace occurs in employee-to-employee relationships, stemming from opposing emotional associations or personal conflicts within relationships, whether personal or task-related. Unlike task conflict, which can frequently be settled moderately

rapidly, relationship clash can be progressing and repetitive in interpersonal interactions [47], making it difficult to settle [48]. Employee stress and strain are thought to be significantly exacerbated by the resulting negative mental states [49]. Employees experiencing relationship clash within a group tend to focus their cognitive energy on interpersonal issues, diverting their mental resources away from strategic challenges and shifting their energy, behavior, and time away from Organizational work [50]. Relationship conflict inhibits the recognition of diverse or conflicting opinions and ideas, thereby hindering overall performance [50]. Moreover, it reduces the occurrence of creative ideas, cognitive flexibility, innovation, and the generation of valuable information that could enhance overall performance [50].

4. Consequences of Perceived Organizational Politics

In this study, the focus is primarily on the outcomes of disruptive employee behavior.

1.5.4.1. Disruptive Employee Behavior

The display of dominance plays a significant role in intentional acts of incivility, as asserted by [51]. Dominance-related motives can be observed in workplace bullying and other uncivil behaviors aimed at asserting control over others. Incivility is often associated with social norms of control and dominance, with individuals in higher hierarchical positions more likely to instigate uncivil behavior [52].

Research Methodology

1.11.1. Study Design

This section presents the research design employed in the study. The current research utilized a quantitative approach along with explanatory research, employing a questionnaire to measure the employees' perceptions of Organizational politics. In support of the study goals, demographic information like gender, age, education level, and work experience were gathered. The research focused on individuals working in both public and private organizations. The research inquiries explored the connections between perceived Organizational politics and its underlying factors (passive leadership, relationship conflict, and Organizational trust), as well as its outcomes on disruptive employee behavior. The questionnaire was utilized to collect data, as it was deemed suitable for examining the variables and their relationships. This research design facilitated the efficient analysis of the significance of perceived Organizational politics within the context of the respondents and the overall population. Moreover, utilizing a survey-based research approach allowed for the collection, organization, tabulation, and interpretation of data. Given that this study aimed to gather data on individuals' perceptions and behaviors, a questionnaire-based survey was the most appropriate mode to employ [53]. The research type employed in this study is both descriptive and causative. This approach enables the description of causal relationships between different variables and provides a framework for data collection and the target population.

1.11.2. Target Population

Employees working in Pakistan's various public and private sectors make up the study's target population, such as banks of the Lahore district of Punjab, Pakistan. The research aimed to collect real-life Organizational data from these organizations. The population of study included 305 individuals who were employed in either public or private organizations.

Organizational politics is a prevalent factor in organizations and has a compelling impact on employee behavior. Employees were deemed the most appropriate population for gathering information and understanding their views, attitudes, perception, and behavior regarding perceived Organizational politics. This was in light of the objective of examining employees' responses to the perception of Organizational politics.

1.11.3. Sample of Study

A sample refers to an accessible and available subset of the target population that is selected in a systematic manner to represent the larger population. In this research, data was collected from the entire targeted population with utmost care. Only participants who had at least one year of job experience in the organization were included in the sample. To alleviate concerns about appraisal apprehension, participants were informed that their participation was voluntary and

could be canceled at any time without penalty, that their responses would be kept confidential, and that only aggregate measurements would be reported. Conducting a census, which involves collecting data from the entire population, is often impractical and costly for larger populations, but it is useful for smaller populations as it helps to eliminate sampling errors [54]. In this study, data was collected from members of the targeted population through a census approach. Out of the 350 distributed questionnaires in printed form directly to the participants of survey, 294 questionnaires were received back and used for data analysis, resulting in a response rate of 85.62%.

1.11.4. Collection of Data

A permission letter was obtained from the administration to seek cooperation from organizations in collecting relevant data from their employees. The collected information from the questionnaires was carefully screened and cleaned to identify and correct any errors in the data.

The respondents of the study were contacted and provided with clear instructions regarding the purpose of the study and the survey questionnaire. A total of 350 survey questionnaires were distributed in printed form to employees in various organizations, with intervals of 2 to 3 days between distributions. The survey period lasted for 15 to 20 days. In total, 299 survey questionnaires were received during the data collection process, resulting in a response rate of 85.42%. Out of the total received questionnaires, 51 were deemed incomplete or improperly filled. For the data analysis process, a total of 350 questionnaires were utilized.

1.11.5. Ethical Considerations

To ensure the research adhered to technical, practical, and ethical standards, the necessary permission to organize the study was acquired from the administration of the University. The data collection process followed the guidelines outlined by [55]. Participants were given clear clarification in regard to the motivation of the review and were helped with finishing the surveys. While demographic information was mandatory, participants were not required to give their names or any other personally identifiable indicators. The confidentiality of the data was maintained, and no information was shared with any unauthorized individuals. The participants were not subjected to any mental or emotional harm, and the questions asked were within ethical boundaries. Their informed consent and well-being were of utmost importance throughout the research process.

1.11.6. Questionnaire Design

This section of the research includes 2 parts. The first section focuses on collecting information related to demographics of survey participants. The demographic information includes gender and age. The gender section allows respondents to select either male or female. The age demographic is categorized into different ranges, such as less than 25, 25-30, 31-35, 36-46, and 46 & above. Additionally, the job experience range is also included, ranging from less than 1 year to more than graduation or above.

The second section of the questionnaire contains the variables that are components of the theoretical framework. A five-point Likert scale is used to measure these variables. The scale ranges from "strongly agree=1" to "strongly disagree=5". This section provides important insights into the perceptions and opinions of the respondents.

Overall, the questionnaire design ensures that relevant demographic information is collected and that the variables of interest are measured using an appropriate Likert scale. This allows for a comprehensive understanding of the respondents' perspectives.

Result and Discussion

The five variables' reliability was evaluated using Cronbach's alpha method. A widely used measure of internal consistency reliability, Cronbach's alpha looks at how interconnected items are within a scale or construct. By calculating Cronbach's alpha, researchers can decide the consistency with which the things inside each scale measure a similar underlying construct. Thus, testing the reliability and validity of the scales utilized in this study is fundamental. Mentioned below are after-effects of validity and reliability analysis:

Table.1 Validity Test

No	Dimension	Item	Validity
1	Perceived Organizational Policies (POP)	Favouritism, rather than merit, promotes people upward in my organization.	0.78
2		Only those who work hard in my organization get rewarded.	0.85
3		People in my organization choose to raise themselves by pulling down others.	0.72
4		If coworkers try to help, it is because they expect something in return, not because they genuinely care about me.	0.76
5		My department has consistently had a significant gathering that nobody at any point crosses.	0.65
6		I have never seen the salary and promotion policies used politically in this division.	0.82
7		People here often hesitate to speak up for fear of reprisal from others.	0.74
8		I've seen policy changes made here that just advance the interests of a couple of people, not the work unit or the company.	0.68
9		Top performers are typically promoted in this department.	0.80
10	Relationship Conflict (RC)	Friction exists in your work groupings.	0.73
11		There are personality clashes in your workgroup.	0.69
12	Organizational Trust (OT)	Your work group is filled with rage.	0.62
13		There is emotional turmoil in your work group.	0.64
14		Employees here believe you can't put trust in this organization.	0.75
15		This organization's employees do things behind your back.	0.71
16	Passive Leadership (PL)	Your supervisor is frequently unavailable when a staff wants assistance with an issue.	0.67

17		Your boss waits till something goes wrong before taking action.	0.70
18	Disruptive Employee Behavior (DEB)	Your boss holds on to taking action until the situation worsens.	0.72
19		Made insulting assertions about you.	0.76
20		You were addressed in an unprofessional manner, either publicly or privately.	0.74
21		Paid little heed to your words or shown little interest in your viewpoints.	0.75
22		Ignored or excluded you from professional socialization (for example, social discussion).	0.71
23		Was dismissive or patronizing to me.	0.73
24		Your judgment on an issue over which you have authority has been questioned.	0.87

The principal objective of this research was to look at the importance of perceived Organizational politics in organizations and its impacts on Organizational efficiency, as well as to focus on the associations between perceived Organizational politics and disruptive employee behavior. In particular, the study focused on the direct and indirect relationships between perceived Organizational politics and its antecedents, as well as its impact on employee behavior inside the organization.

Data was gathered from employees of a variety of public and private organizations using survey questionnaires. The distribution of the questionnaires took place over a period of 3 to 4 weeks, with intervals of 2 to 3 days between distributions. A total of 350 questionnaires were distributed, and 299 of them were returned and considered for analysis. The survey instrument consisted of 27 items in total, with 9 items related to the measurement of perceived Organizational politics, 5 items assessing relationship conflict, 5 items capturing passive leadership, 2 items examining Organizational trust, and 7 items addressing disruptive employee behavior. Additionally, 4 items were included to gather demographic information.

In order to guarantee the construct's legitimacy and dependability, a number of analyses were carried out. This included working out Cronbach's alpha, performing exploratory component examination, evaluating the credibility of each section, and leading a progression of other element investigations. Descriptive statics and correlation analysis were also used for preliminary analyses.

The instruments used in the study were as follows: The Perceived Organizational Politics Scale (POPS) evolved by [56] was employed to measure employees' perceived Organizational politics. The Disruptive Employee Behavior Scale (DEB) developed by [10] was used to measure disruptive employee behavior. Organizational trust was measured using a two-item, five-point instrument evolved by Daley. Passive leadership was assessed using a five-item scale adapted from [32], two items from [57], and one item specifically developed for this study.

By employing these instruments and conducting the necessary analyses, the study aimed to provide insights into the relationship between perceived Organizational politics, its antecedents, and disruptive employee behavior, thus contributing to the existing literature on these topics. The current study's findings revealed that perceived Organizational politics is favorably associated to passive leadership, relationship conflict, and disruptive employee behavior while being negatively related to Organizational trust. The following are the answers to the preceding questions:

1. Does passive leadership have an effect on the perception of Organizational politics?

The findings align with previous research [58] that indicated passive leadership negatively influences employee behavior. According to the grand base theory (cite grand base theory), passive leadership, marked by a lack of proactive involvement and inaction, creates a void that may lead to employees perceiving higher levels of Organizational politics. This substantiates the hypothesis that an increase in passive leadership corresponds to an increase in perceived Organizational politics (POP), whereas a decrease in passive leadership results in decreased POP.

2. Does relationship conflict influence perceived Organizational politics?

As employees engage in rude and conflicting behavior with their colleagues, this hostile environment fosters the perception of Organizational politics. Therefore, an increase in relationship conflict corresponds to an increase in perceived Organizational politics (POP), while less conflict in relationships reduces the perception of Organizational politics at work.

3. Does Organizational trust impact perceived Organizational politics?

As inferred from social exchange theory and the preceding chapter's results, Organizational trust, deeply embedded in repeated interactions and reciprocity [59], plays a critical role. In the context of the grand base theory, it was expected that the absence of Organizational trust would lead to a higher perception of Organizational politics and contribute to a negative perception of the workplace.

4. Does passive leadership affect disruptive employee behavior?

Passive managers failing to enforce positive norms and address poor behavior may inadvertently encourage an environment in which disruptive behavior flourishes. This affirms our expectation of a positive relationship between passive leadership and disruptive employee behavior.

5. Does relationship conflict impact disruptive employee behavior?

Chapter 4's results and the associated discussion mirror previous findings [9] highlighting the correlation between relationship conflict and disruptive employee behavior. These minor acts of mistreatment, encompassed by disruptive employee behavior, can have significant consequences for organizations, supporting the grand base theory's claim.

6. What is the impact of Organizational trust on disruptive employee behavior?

Our findings align with previous research [58] that indicates when Organizational trust is lacking, employees may harbor hostile intentions towards colleagues and supervisors. This absence of trust can lead to increased disruptive employee behavior [60]. Conversely, in the presence of high Organizational trust, the likelihood of disruptive employee behavior decreases [52].

7. Does perceived Organizational politics influence disruptive employee behavior?

Empirical evidence from past studies [61] confirms that perceived Organizational politics is associated with uncivil and aggressive behaviors directed at individuals perceived to engage in political actions within the organization. This finding supports the premise of the grand base theory (cite grand base theory), illustrating that employees who perceive Organizational politics may engage in disruptive employee behavior towards those they associate with such political behaviors.

8. Does employee behavior change as result of the perception of Organizational politics?

The perception of Organizational politics significantly influences employee behavior. According to the grand base theory, the perception of Organizational politics fosters negative attitudes towards organizational activities, potentially leading to rude behavior and intentions to harm the organization.

Conclusion

This chapter marks the culmination of our exploration into the intricate relationship between perceived Organizational politics and disruptive employee behavior within the diverse landscape of banking organizations. Through rigorous research and data analysis, our study has delivered insights that resonate with the hypotheses that were initially proposed. Organizational politics significantly influences disruptive employee behavior. Passive leadership contributes significantly to the perception of Organizational politics, leading to an increase in disruptive behavior. Relationship conflict is positively correlated with perceived Organizational politics, contributing to higher disruptive behavior. Organizational trust acts as a stabilizing factor, decreasing the likelihood of disruptive employee behavior. Perceived Organizational politics has a significant impact on disruptive employee behavior, creating a cascade effect within the workplace.

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